

The Plan and the Chemical Industries*

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Acharya P. C. Ray is acknowledged to be the father of chemical research in India and could be regarded as one of the pioneers of the Freedom movement. He was not only a great chemist, but he was a humanist with deep sympathies. He had many qualities of mind which is rare in one single individual. But he was to a large extent indebted to some of his brilliant pupils for the propagation of his ideas. Of those, the late J. C. Ghosh was one who inherited most of the master's qualities and to a large extent was responsible for the ideals of Acharya Ray taking roots in the soil. Ghosh was not only a brilliant research worker but was a very successful teacher. He had the tact of P. C. Ray. He was an orator of renown and writer of good English prose and Bengali. He had the charitable trait of P. C. Ray and had been a strong supporter of men who had dedicated their careers to the service of the country. Many a freedom fighter was supported by him and many owed their individual liberty to the risk he took to shelter them at the hour of peril. He was a strong disciplinarian and was a successful administrator. His work at Dacca and the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, is well known. It is not necessary to recapitulate it here. The short time he was the Vice-Chancellor of the Calcutta University, he was able to leave his mark on the administration. He was Director-General of Industries and Supply at Delhi soon after independence. There he had ample scope to guide the destiny of future industrial development of India. It was there, the writer was intimately connected with him in his work and knew the views he held. The planning Commission had not yet been formed. India then had huge sterling balance and judicious handling of the situation was needed. This was done to such good purpose that in 1949-50, the balance was still mounting up and an urgent appeal from U.K. was received to liberalise the imports so that the pressure on British monetary resources could somewhat be relieved. Compared to the position obtaining then, we have only to think what the position is today to understand why the Planning has to be done realistically. Later on, after the formation of the Planning Commission, Ghosh was chosen as a member. Unfortunately, the work he began there he could not complete and he died in harness. His grit could be understood when it is known that even when the haemoglobin content of his blood had fallen to 28%, he was still carrying on, as he felt that he must try to do to his last day, the task he had set himself to do. Therefore, it is in fitness of things that I shall talk of Planning as tribute to his memory.

HISTORY OF PLANNING IN INDIA

The late Sir M. Visvesvaraya, the renowned statesman, published in 1934 a book called the "Planned Economy for India". This was perhaps the first attempt to plan an

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economic reconstruction of India. This book did not receive the attention it deserved because India was not then free and the voice of a nationalist had not much influence on the rulers of the land. Three years later, Subhas Chandra Bose, the then Congress President, appointed a Planning Committee under the Chairmanship of J. L. Nehru. Ghosh was then in Bangalore at the Indian Institute of Science and was chosen a member of this committee. Another celebrated scientist was also chosen but he declined to accept membership for fear of offending the rulers. This committee's work was delayed due to various reasons and it could not submit its report till 1948, i.e. after independence. But some Bombay industrialists submitted a plan to the nation in 1943. The broad objective of this plan was to raise agricultural production by 130% and the industrial output by 500%. Top priority was given to basic industries. The plan aimed at increasing the per capita income by 100%, i.e. to raise it from Rs. 85 to 130. Almost simultaneously with the Bombay Plan, M. N. Roy, the noted Marxist, prepared a "People's Plan". It was a ten-year plan involving an outlay of Rs. 15,000 crores. Agriculture and consumer goods industry received the highest priority, but basic industries were relegated to a secondary position. In addition to the Bombay and People's Plan, there appeared an idealist plan known as the Gandhian Plan, which wanted to establish a decentralised economy with self-sufficient villages. The development of cottage industries was the main objective of this plan.

In August, 1944, the Government of India felt that if they turned a deaf ear to the demands for a planned economy, they stood to lose much more ground and the war-effort was bound to suffer. They created the Department of Planning and Development and put Sir Ardeahir Dalal, an industrialist and one of the authors of the Bombay Plan, in charge of this development department. This department, as soon as it was formed, published the famous "Industrial Policy" resolution of the Government of India. In this it was stated that certain industries like armament production, railway, communication would be in the Government sphere and virtually left the entire field to private enterprise. This resolution underwent many changes with the passage of time—many industries in the private sector were transferred to the public sector—but virtually it recognised the co-existence of both the private and public sectors. During the period of interim Government, prior to independence, the Planning and Development Department, established in 1944, was abolished. This gave rise to much criticism but it was felt that since the division of sphere of activity between the Private and Public sector had been well defined, the Industries Department would be well able to plan the development of the Public sector and the Private sector would look after the development in their field through Trade Associations, Chambers of Commerce, and the Development Councils formed by the Government. But in 1950, the Planning Commission was formed with Mr. Nehru as chairman. In 1951, the Planning Commission presented the first five-year plan covering the period 1951 to 56.

THE FIRST FIVE-YEAR PLAN

The first plan was conceived modestly. Its main concern was to combat the prevailing inflationary situation and food shortage. Rafi Ahmed Kidwai, a member of the cabinet, exercised his influence to give agriculture due prominence as he wisely felt that from a purely agricultural economy of thousands of years, no transformation to an industrial

economy could take place without disaster. Throughout the first five-year plan, the government endeavoured to widen the sphere of the Public sector, but this did not mean that there was any programme of nationalisation. The Private sector was allowed to expand and enjoyed a free scope for earning legitimate profit. This resulted in free flow of capital and there was confidence about India's ability to run its house in an orderly manner. But there was a noticeable fly in the ointment. Certain industries like the tea industry, which had earned major part of India's foreign exchange, became the target of attack of some interested people and was Indianised. Many such industries were acquired by Indian nationals. This resulted in diminished efficiency but what is worse, a large amount of money was spent in repatriating foreign capital while India was clamouring for the flow of more capital. I had long discussion on the subject with Prof. Ghosh and he entirely agreed that we should hasten slowly. He was not a member of the Planning Commission then.

The main feature of the first Plan was an outlay of Rs. 2,069/- crores which was raised to Rs. 2,378 crores, but the actual amount spent was perhaps Rs. 1900 crores. This was less than 4% of India's national income. Agriculture received the highest priority and 42% of the total amount was spent on agriculture. This was fully justified. A growing economy must have agriculture as its base. If food products cost too much, it means that the cost of industrial labour would be high and consequently production cost of factories would be high. The late H. K. Sen had calculated in 1924, that labour must have an equivalent of the price of 3 Mds. of cereals he eats as his minimum wage. I have never known a more accurate guess. In every instance, I have found this rule to be generally true. Therefore, our hearts were gladdened when we found that agricultural production increased by 18%. Food production rose from 60 million tons to 65 million tons during the last year of the plan. Among the cash crops, oil seeds and cotton exceeded the plan target. In the field of electricity generation, the installed capacity increased by 1.1 million KW. From the above it would appear that in the field of agriculture, irrigation, and power generation, the first plan was a noticeable success.

INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION

Industrial production during the first plan was 40% over the years. It was 148 in 1954, taking the base 1946—100. Cloth production increased by 400 million yards, cement by 1.9 million tons. Paper, paper products, chemical industry including heavy chemicals all showed significant increase, largely due to availability of raw materials needed from abroad. This was possible as the foreign exchange position was rather easy and drastic cut in imports was not necessary. This was in a sense unfortunate as it gave rise to the feeling that once an industry was established, irrespective of how much imported components were involved, means will be found to keep it going somehow. A large number of investors, who had no knowledge or experience of chemical industry, were drawn into the field. They were mostly guided by the advice of their foreign collaborators who would advise them to embark on a project even if the percentage of imported components and materials were pretty high. The government then had no effective machinery to check this tendency as the only way they could intervene was when the floated new capital came to the Examiner of Capital issues for examination. That was hardly a time to intervene effectively. To remedy this defect, the Control and Regulation of Industries Act was passed in 1953. But by then, certain notions were so ingrained in the minds of entrepreneurs

that effective checks could not be imposed. Then there was the question of influence. To cite one instance, a firm was permitted to collaborate with a foreign firm to manufacture such pedestrian items like magnesium sulphate, ferrous sulphate, lactate, etc. But in many cases these so-called foreign collaborators insisted on the semifinished raw materials being imported from their home principals; in many cases the price demanded was much above the world price and had to be paid. The original idea was that in the initial period, some essential raw materials would be allowed to be imported, but no phased programme of their manufacture in the country was laid down. If such a condition was laid down, there was no effective machinery to impose the condition. Moreover, towards the end of the first five-year plan, it was apparent that there would be shortage of foreign exchange. Hence the policy of not getting more than one firm in a particular field was followed, perhaps unconsciously and this created monopolies which had undoubtedly contributed to much of our trouble today.

THE GROWTH OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY IN THE FIRST PLAN

It is not possible to give an idea of the growth of the industry in a lecture like this. Those who are interested may consult "Indian Chemical & Pharmaceutical Industry—1963 Survey", issued by the Indian Chemical Manufacturers Association. It is sufficient to say that the Sindri fertiliser factory, planned in 1946, came into production in this period and the Pimpri Antibiotic factory was planned. There was noticeable increase in the production of basic chemicals like acids, alkalis, dyes, rubber, some plastics, and some organic chemicals. But if an analysis is made, it will be found that we did not pay adequate thought to the problem of imports which these industries required to function well. To take the instance of sulphuric acid, capacity was increased to 500,000 tons in 1960, but no provision was made to produce sulphur. For feeding plants of this dimension to full capacity, the import requirement of sulphur is nearly 170,000 tons. There were other industries needing sulphur. The import bill is colossal. Yet there was a proposal to recover sulphur from gypsum (by-product cement), the utilisation of Bihar and Simla Pyrites, the recovery of sulphur from the waste gases of copper smelting works, but nothing was actually done. Today the capacity of sulphuric acid plants have been further increased. The result is that owing to the shortage of sulphur due to foreign exchange crisis, many plants are running much below capacity. The freight on sulphur in American ships is much higher than other shipping lines, but we are powerless to use the cheapest transport. The fertiliser factory at Sindri uses gypsum in place of sulphuric acid, but transportation costs are high owing to the material having to be transferred from narrow to standard gauge. The new fertiliser factories will produce urea, ammonium nitrate, and nitrochalk. Then another point, which was overlooked, was that the size of sulphuric acid plant for which a licence was given. We have allowed many units under 10 tons, many under 50 tons. There are only a few over 50 tons. This should never have been done.

However, without going into details, it was realised that the slow progress in the industrial sector, particularly chemical, in the first five-year plan was due to unpreparedness and lack of technical personnel. The low level of steel production was responsible for the inadequate development of capital goods. I think this conclusion is liable to be challenged. The real reason for the slow growth of the capital goods industry was the defective training which our engineers received and really were incapable of producing

anything new, neither were they able to copy existing equipment even when there was no restriction of patents. Moreover, till lately we had not thought of producing alloy steel, which should have been done if we were serious about manufacturing capital goods needed for the chemical industry.

THE SECOND PLAN

The production of Iron and Steel received the highest priority. Steel plants have been set up at Bhilai, Rourkela, and Durgapur. There was a plan to erect a fourth plant at Bokaro. The American view was that it would be beset with many difficulties. At first, we thought of going our own way and do it ourselves. Consultants were appointed but we have changed our mind now and are relying on the Russians. The Plant has yet to come into being. There has been a lot of public discussion about this venture. It is not proper for me to express any views now. Let us wait and see. But it would be pertinent to record here that in 1945, India produced the cheapest steel in the world, but what is the position today? The steel plants are still losing money and the steel produced is the most costly in the world. Yet we hoped that by exporting Iron and Steel products we would earn some foreign exchange to pay some of our borrowed capital. But it would be incorrect to say that we are not exporting any. Thanks to the "incentive bonus" which we have given to the exporters, they are able to export at much below the cost of production and they make good their losses by importing scarce and short supply items and selling these at enormous profits to the manufacturing concerns who need badly these imported raw materials. The result is not only inflation but whatever little chance these manufacturers had of exporting their own products vanish into the thin air. If a soap manufacturer cannot import his own requirement of tallow and coconut oil and has to buy these from those who can import these through their "Incentive Bonus", naturally buying tallow and coconut oils at high price, he cannot expect to export his soap. In the second plan, it was hoped that there would be appreciable development of heavy engineering, machine building, and chemical industries. It was hoped that there would be greater utilization of installed capacities, but when imports of imported ingredients had to be drastically curtailed how could one expect to achieve this desideratum!

During the second plan period, India started manufacturing many new items which undoubtedly had export potentiality. But in most cases, due to careless planning, this remained a vain hope. To take the example of saccharin, only one firm has been licensed to produce chlorosulphonic acid, while there are dozens of contact sulphuric acid plants. The result is that chlorosulphonic acid is not available in reasonable quantities at a reasonable price. The government allowed the import of *o*-toluenesulphonamide from abroad. The idea was that it would be oxidised to saccharin locally. But no one bothered to get parties interested in the production of permanganate in the country. There is one firm producing it, and the present selling price of potassium permanganate is Rs. 6 per kilo! How could any one produce saccharin at this price and export. The consuming public, thanks to our ailed economy, has to pay the price or go without it. The same remark applies to isoniazide. We have to import gamma picolin, but there had been a lot of talk about producing it locally and nothing has been done. We have no foreign exchange to buy it from the cheapest market abroad but have to accept it from any source who accepts payments in currency we can afford. The cost is high and added to that is the price of per-

manganate. Hundreds of similar instances can be quoted. Therefore, the hope that idle capacity would be utilised in the second plan remained a pious hope.

The review of the second plan showed that it was hoped deficit financing to the extent of Rs. 1200 crores would not put too great a strain on the Indian economy and somehow we would be able to strengthen the capital base by increased productivity and technical efficiency. How far we have been able to achieve these, is too patent to merit a detailed discussion. But we had been able to increase the investment as a proportion of total income from 8% to 11%. But savings as a proportion of national income seem to have remained constant at 8%. This discrepancy in saving investment rates was made good by import surpluses, financed out of our sterling balances and foreign aid loans. Therefore, it would be evident that the increase in investment that had taken place depended largely on foreign exchange reserves and external assistance. This latter we got in a generous measure. A mentality of borrowing grew up and we are trying to borrow as much as we can and get, without a thought for the morrow. I shall comment on this later on.

A review of the second plan forces the conclusion that the planners concentrated too much on what theoretically could be done and they were not practical enough to understand how it could be done!

Agricultural planning in the first plan also had a few defects. The most notable one was that there was no crop planning. After the fragmentation of holding, the individual share of land of a farmer was too small for him to get a living out of it. Increased use of fertilisers cannot do a miracle. A person holding, say, a bigha of land and having four or five mouths to feed, naturally has to look to other avenues of employment. There were new opportunities of employments as industrial labour in nearby towns. Therefore, he cannot be blamed if he left his land to the care of the women folk and came to earn his living. This happened to such a large extent that the production was much less than could have been. This could have been avoided to a certain extent if there were cottage or semi-large scale industries established in the villages where he could have earned something in his spare time, which is considerable in agriculture. The only effort that was made was to boost up traditional industries like handloom where peasant has little chance of employment. How far this policy of fragmentation of holding is responsible for low agricultural production is a serious matter for thought and there should be no sentimentality in this. How Indian agriculture stands in comparison with other nations would be evident from the following table.

Yield of rice per acre.

India	870 lb.	Italy	3200 lb.
Brazil	1020	Thailand	1240
Burma	1500	China	1560
Japan	2720	Egypt	2920

Yield of wheat per acre.

India	760	France	2140
Australia	1010	Japan	2430
U.S.A.	1440	Denmark	3700
Poland	1780		

Those who think that mere increased application of fertilisers would do the miracle must ponder to think why the yield in some of the advanced countries is so low despite their having plenty of fertilisers. One thing is quite clear that an agriculturist must have sufficiently big holding to make it pay. Co-operative farming, which has been suggested as a remedy, will not work in this country as it has not worked in China and Russia. The agricultural policy of Russia has undergone considerable change in recent years and one should not be surprised if it undergoes more far-reaching changes. The writing is on the wall.

Those who think that drastic cut in the imports of food grains could be made will be sadly disillusioned. No great advance can be made in the industrial sphere unless more foreign exchange is available for raw materials and this could only be possible if we become self-sufficient in food. It is no use establishing new industries and investing borrowed capital into it, if foreign-exchange problem keeps them idle. Even when the main raw material is indigenous, there are difficulties. In 1947, India was the cheapest producer of benzene in the world. Our cost of production was six annas a gallon or 6d. Now the price of benzene has gone up. The policy hitherto has been to charge a price what the market can bear. Today, the largest outlet of benzene is in the manufacture of styrene, but the situation would be more serious when the Hindusthan Organic Chemicals and Durgapur Chemicals are ready to go into production. Some firms contemplating to produce phenol and phthalic anhydride from naphthalene would find it uneconomical to produce these as the present price of benzene is Rs. 2.83 per gallon ex-coke ovens. There is also an excise duty of 5%. The cost of transport of benzene is high. The landed cost of benzene at the site of manufacture would come to Rs. 900 per ton as against the prevailing international price of Rs. 380-400 per ton. When we exported benzene, we did it at Rs. 200 per ton. In U.S.A., benzene is available at 3.4 cent per lb. and thus polystyrene is sold at 12 cent per lb., detergent alkylate at 9.7 cent per lb., aniline at 15 cent per lb., phenol at 12.2 cent. per lb. If we start industries at the present price of benzene, then the consumer would have to undergo still further handicaps. Why the price of benzene has increased so enormously is a matter which should be investigated. But one thing is certain that we have paid far too much for the coke ovens and the depreciation has to be borne by the limited production. Therefore, it would appear that further expansion in the synthetics derived from benzene, toluene, naphthalene, and xylene would be suicidal.

This brings us to the crux of the problem—why our production cost in every sphere is high? In our haste to industrialise, we have paid scant attention to what we are paying for capital goods and what price we are paying for foreign collaboration. We have made no attempts to produce any worthwhile plant and equipment ourselves. We have not given proper training to our thousands, nay lakhs, of graduates we have produced since independence. We have increased the number of universities without thinking if we have adequate number of reliable teachers and professors. Japan was faced with similar difficulties arising out of their increasing the number of universities after World War II, but they have nicely circumvented the difficulties. Could we not have taken a lesson from that? The other reason why our production cost is high is our labour inefficiency. In U.S.A., one man looks after 1000 spindles in a day, while the corresponding figure in India, is 11.5 men. Cloth production per worker in U.S.A. comes to 45060 yds. per annum against 17717 yds. in India. This is true about almost every factory. Compared to 1946, per capita

output in a steel plant is now barely 60 per cent. The labour bill now is about 3-4 times that of 1946. In industries where mechanisation was possible, we have not been able to do it, due to various pressures. Humanitarian considerations have led us to employ 5 men where the work could have been done by 1. This is particularly true about the public sector ventures which, with one or two exceptions, are all running at a loss. It is easy to pass the blame on to our lack of management training, but many of the captains of industry in the past had not much of formal education. They succeeded because they had power of hard work and a keen desire to succeed. In a public sector enterprise, the profit motive is not the concern of the paid officers of the management.

The high cost of production is also to a certain extent due to callousness with which self-employed artisans like carpenters, plumbers, masons, etc. do their work. In many factories these men are employed for temporary repair work. Any one familiar with their work will know that a minor repair work takes at least 8 to 10 times the time than previously. As these men are employed on a daily basis, the cost becomes high. There are certain foreign nationals, whom many do not like to employ because of recent political reasons, do these jobs at a fraction of the time and better. Although their daily wage is higher, it is cheaper in the long run to employ them. Our planners have told the people that they are trying to usher in a socialistic pattern of society (which perhaps has given rise to the mistaken notion that one will not have to work hard): they should tell them now that "survival of the fittest" is an inexorable law of nature. Any amount of foreign aid will not be able to save the country unless premium is put on hard work.

FINANCING OF THE SECOND PLAN

The second plan envisaged a doubling of public expenditure from Rs. 2400 crores of the first plan to Rs. 4800 crores in the second plan. The general investment target for the entire economy was set at Rs. 6,200 crores. Not only the expenditure target of the second plan was much higher than the first, but import requirements were much higher because of the emphasis on heavy industries. Deficit financing started in the first plan was on a much larger scale. The implications of these were not fully realised. We are today beginning to realise the mistake.

THE THIRD PLAN

The perils of deficit financing was apparently realised, as in the third plan this was reduced to only 550 crores. It was realised by the planners that there would be considerable shortage of foreign exchange. Third plan started with a low level of foreign exchange reserves. The planners expressed the hope that there would be considerable curtailment of imports. I have mentioned that the establishment of every single industry means a perpetual commitment for importing ingredients. How the planners hoped there would be curtailment of imports is not readily understood unless like Mr. Micawber, they hoped that something would turn up. Secondly, they hoped that the rising price line would be held — a hope which received support from the highest in the land. If the price line was held, the planners felt that the level of investment would rise from 11% to 20%. How the price line has been held is common knowledge and we need not go into that.

The dangers of deficit financing was realised by Dr. J. C. Ghosh. He had long discussion on this subject with the writer. On one occasion, a celebrated economist was present. He was of the opinion that deficit financing can succeed under a dictatorship but not otherwise. Ghosh held the view that strict control can take the place of dictatorship. But the writer thought, strict control can succeed only if there is scrupulous honesty. Some say that controls have brought in their wake unbridled dishonesty and corruption, but some responsible Ministers have assured us that there is not much corruption. Perhaps the latter view is right but one begins to wonder why then are the sadachar committees?

It was hoped that in the third plan period there would be profits accruing from the investments in the public sector. The following will show how far that has been right:

Public investment.	Year.	Loss.
1090.75 crores	1961	10.6 crores
1294.11	1962/63	12.36 crores
1773.59	1963/64	55.13 lakhs

It is heartening to see that the loss has been reduced. But will there be any profit some day? How far distant is that date? If under monopoly conditions, we cannot run a business to show profit, then there is something wrong somewhere. Before we venture on more costly programmes, we should lay our finger on the weak spot. The apologists say that we have no management experience, but that is oversimplification of a problem vitally affecting the nation. The labour inefficiency, the lack of desire on the part of every one to put in a day's honest work, the interference from politically influential people might be some of the reasons. The writer thinks that we have failed to give adequate education to our chemists and other scientists. There is consensus of opinion that the standard of education is much lower now than it had been ever before. There is a body sitting to go into this question and we can leave the matter to them. There is only one suggestion that I wish to make—it is time we pay scant attention to the academic distinction of a candidate in selecting him for a post. It is necessary that he should have a practical bent of mind and should be temperamentally suited for the post. Psychological tests are more important than the production of a first class diploma. There have been organisations to spot scientific talent in the young. These organisations go by the result of examination papers mostly. It is far more important that a candidate, who shows ingenuity in devising a common experiment or produce an article made by his own hand, which shows promise, should be preferred to one who has answered an examination paper well. I know of a person who has designed toy prototype of a jet engine but he is hopeless when told to write something. Another person, who could not continue his studies because of poverty, designed an automatic device for shutting off a motor used for lifting water when the tanks were full. He had similar other useful devices. He went from door to door and no body took any notice of him. He has volumes of correspondence with the government. The late B. C. Roy put him in contact with an English firm who bought his patent outright for Rs. 8000 and took a patent in U.K., where it is being manufactured now. He has spent his money in further experiments in his own home and now is at the end of his tether.

FOREIGN EXCHANGE

The planners realised that in the third plan, there would be great scarcity of foreign exchange and the remedy that suggested itself to them was an export drive. The foreign

exchange position has been the constant vigil of the Commerce Ministry. At present, we are exporting about Rs. 900 crores worth of goods annually. There is some jubilation that our efforts are succeeding. A moment's thought will show how hollow is the victory. It is true that foreigners are interested in our mineral ores and they are taking every thing they can. We are depriving the future generations of valuable expendable resources. Some countries have taken the trouble to build railway line from the mines to the port so that the ores move quickly and are entering into long-term contracts before we change our minds. There has been no protests about this except from an organisation of Geologists and Mining Engineers. It is about time other organisations thought about the matter. Selling these ores, *ad lib*, is like meeting your daily expenses by selling heirloom of the family. In some directions, we are selling to foreign countries, our home produced articles like sugar at a loss of about Rs. 30 crores a year. This loss is being made good by making the home consumers pay more. Yet our avowed objective in the third plan was to hold the price line! The matter is more serious when we consider the export of some items, the major components of which we import by paying hard currency. To take the case of refrigerators: we are selling these to a foreign country at Rs. 900/- per piece, while imported components cost us much more in dollars. The importing country saves its dollars. We think this a very friendly gesture on the part of our benefactors. The same refrigerator costs a consumer in the country Rs. 2500. Is this the way to hold the price line!

I have mentioned about the bonus scheme to improve exports. Every consumer of imported raw materials knows to his cost how that has contributed to the inflation.

Our plans to large-scale export to neighbouring countries would not be easy to materialise as every country is following the same policy as ours in establishing new industries, not only with a view to be self-sufficient but every one has export as their objective. To take the instance of glass industry: Singapore has established a large factory with a view to exporting to neighbouring countries and then there is Japan, China, and Hongkong. How can we compete unless we sell at a much lower price than our cost of production? We produce about 140 crores of rupees worth of rubber products, paints and glass ware. We have exported only 2 crores of rupees worth in 1964. The following table will show why our cost of production is high.

Raw material.	India.	U.K.	U.S.A.
Soda ash	4.25 c/lb.	1.8 c/lb.	1.6 c/lb.
Rubber	38.8 c/lb.	23.1 c/lb.	23.0 c/lb.
Carbon black	Rs. 2.14/kg.	Rs. 1.04/kg.	Rs. 0.78/kg.
Isobutanol	Rs. 4.5/kg.	Rs.	Rs. 1.4/kg.
Titanium dioxide	Rs. 6.5/kg.	Rs. 1.1/kg.	Rs. 0.78/kg.

The same position holds with regard to other basic raw materials. The price of nitric acid is 4-6 times that of the world price. The government, in order to lower the price, has advised manufacturers to import Chilean nitre! Where would the foreign exchange come from! One hand of the Government does not know what the other hand is doing! What is wrong with the oxidation of ammonia! The justification for importing nitre is, that as there is shortage of sodium sulphate, this could be sold as a by-product. India's consumption of soda ash now stands at 338,000 tons p.a. and caustic soda at 282,000 tons p.a. The high cost cannot be laid to the door of low production. If we have to bring these

basic industries to a level of efficiency, the uneconomical units must go and efforts should be made to make some of the units to merge. There has been no production of sulphur yet. Some efforts should be made to hasten this. It is no use allowing capacity to increase if there is no foreign exchange to import the sulphur. At one time, great hopes were entertained about our pharmaceutical exports. Although we have established the manufacture of vitamins, antibiotics, and other synthetic drugs, our cost of production precludes us from exporting any. Vitamin C, produced in India, cost about Rs. 80 per kilo, whereas the landed cost of the imported product is round about Rs. 27 per kilo.

FOREIGN EXCHANGE POSITION

We have already incurred a debt of 6 billion dollars and the interest and the part payment of the principal would cost about Rs. 2700 crores in foreign exchange in the next plan period. If we take Rs. 5400 crores of rupees as our foreign exchange earning in this period, then there would be left about Rs. 2700 crores for various imports including the raw material for the industries. If we do not establish any further industries, the amount available would not be sufficient to keep the existing industries in 50% production. Yet there is talk about plunging deeper in the mire! The Prime Minister, soon after he assumed office, made a very important statement, *i.e.* he did not think that we should lightly indulge in more deficit financing.

THE FOURTH PLAN

Preparations of the fourth plan are now nearing completion. The main economic aspects are clear. A growth rate of about 7% and expansion of employment are being aimed at. This will mean doubling the outlay of the third plan. At the same time, the stability of the economy is to be preserved by developing agriculture and avoiding deficit financing. The idea is to increase the production of the consumer goods. On the other hand, there is uncovered gap in the resources: it is to be met through larger exports! All these postulates are wishful thinking. A realist will know better. The extent to which needs of defence will require diversion of resources is anybody's guess. The present political situation does not leave much room for optimism. The Prime Minister started with a pragmatic approach to the fourth plan and in view of coming general elections, the political approach to the fourth plan may easily prevail over the commonsense point of view. But it is pertinent to point out that the rising prices and consequent hardships and the total inability of supplies of commodities keeping pace with the demand may easily nullify the advantages which the political strategists expect to get from an ambitious plan. The gaps in the industrial structure have more or less throttled the third plan and this will be the mill stone round the neck of the fourth plan. We must not forget that a cable unit at Kotah ran out of imported raw materials and closed down in March last, and another in Bombay came to the end of their miseries in April due to the same cause. The fertiliser industry is extremely worried about the rock-phosphate position: lack of sufficient sulphur has slowed down the superphosphate industry. Many engineering firms in Calcutta are thinking of closing down. Our efforts to seek more non-project aid has not been very successful and in future we cannot expect a radical change in the situation. These are hard facts which we must remember before we are led away by our enthusiasm. We must examine the reason why so many key industries have fallen behind the targets of the third plan. Why is it that pumps

and compressor project or heavy ball bearing project have still to get off the ground, even though the Soviet credits for these had been tied up in advance of the third plan? The alloy steel plant at Durgapur got such a late start, it is necessary to examine the reason why. These delays have added to the burden of engineering industries as these products, had they been manufactured, would have relieved the import burden of the consuming factories. There is a lot of discussion going on about the size of the fourth plan. We hear that the plan size would be Rs. 22,500 crores. Those who are studying the plight of our chemical industries hope that so far as the chemical industries are concerned, let the fourth plan be one of consolidation rather of new expansion. There are thousands of scientists engaged in the C.S.I.R. Let their services be utilised in solving the imported raw material problem, problems of method and equipment. Let the intermediate factory, which should have received the highest priority, be accelerated.

The C.S.I.R. scientists will have to change their outlook. The object of C.S.I.R. is not to train students for the Ph. D. degree or do theoretical research. This should be left to the universities. We have now to investigate alternative processes of manufacture so that a particular process involving the import of costly imported equipment can be replaced by one which can be performed with entirely indigenous material. As an example, the case of reduction of esters by high pressure hydrogen and copper chromite can be taken. A process has been developed which requires no importation of capital equipment. It should be in our interest to adopt a process even if the ultimate yield is slightly lower, if that means avoiding of foreign exchange. There are other problems awaiting solution. We import rock-phosphate—some factories are closing down because we can't import enough—yet the Trichy phosphatic nodules are there. Some one has to find out how the associated carbonates could be freed from it. Then there is Assam coal which has about 10% of sulphur in some cases. A method is required for the economical recovery of sulphur. How much foreign exchange can be saved!

The Assam coal has also germanium in it. We have no known sources of germanium. If we want our semiconductor industry to develop, we must find out a method for recovering germanium from it. There are hundreds of problems like this which the C.S.I.R. could have taken in hand. But then this kind of investigation does not lead to academic glory.

J. C. Ghosh died before the second plan was completed. He did not have any chance to shape the third plan. Had he been alive, I am sure, many of the pitfalls of the third plan could have been avoided. He was an idealist but like his teacher Acharya Ray, he was essentially a practical man. He did not live in ivory tower all the time.

What manner of man was Ghosh? Some say that he was a leftist. I do not know about that. I know this much that he always stood for doing the "right" thing. This often used to displease his pronounced leftist friends. He was uncompromising when duty was concerned. He could not tolerate any idleness or lame excuses. Yet he never lost his temper. He had a mild sarcasm which was enough.

I often wonder what would have been his reaction to the general fall in efficiency prevailing today.

If a plan is to succeed, the first thing necessary is to realise that a first class nation

cannot be built up with tenth rate people. We must realise that we have not only rights under the constitution, but we have also inherent obligation to do our duty. Trane told me in conversation, after he toured India to see how were our plans working, that unless there is mass enthusiasm for a plan, no plan can succeed. I added that along with enthusiasm there should be hard work and a keen sense of duty, to which he readily agreed.

I hope that our planners would try to awaken mass enthusiasm in the fourth plan and remove the causes which have led to the fall in standards in every direction, including education, moral behaviour and work. J. C. Ghosh would have tried that had he been alive.